

Visiting the Margins.

INnovative **CULT**ural **ToURisM** in European peripheries

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1. Introduction

This report presents the final results of the INCULTUM project in its public version, as described in the Grant Agreement. This report completes the documentation presented throughout the project and is the continuation of the D1.3 Progress report (M24), therefore we present here the results of the last year of the project on each work package. In order to try to avoid repetition of information, which may not be very fruitful, we will refer in many cases to the results presented in other deliverables, making direct reference to them. Due to the fact that some WPs have presented their final deliverables on this same date, we will not deal with these results here, but will redirect the reader directly to them. These are the cases of:

- WP2 Communication and dissemination: this WP and its responsible partner (PROMOTER) have submitted the final deliverable where a general summary of all the activities of this WP is made, not only in the last year of the project, but throughout the whole duration of the project. Therefore, we consider that the review of this deliverable is more than enough to have a global knowledge of the results of WP2. We refer to **D2.3. Report on dissemination and communication** (M36).
- WP5 Communities of practice, innovative tools and pilot solutions: the **D5.2 Final pilots report** (M36) provides an in-depth overview of the 10 INCULTUM pilots during project. It also presents a summary of the main findings and innovations in each pilot.
- WP7 Impact, evaluation and exploitation plan_in the case of this WP, **D7.3 Updated plan for the impact, evaluation and exploitation of results** has been submitted. This deliverable contains the decisive updated version of the Impact, evaluation and exploitation plan, elaborated on the basis of continuous tracking of the effectiveness of the activities and, crucially, the feed-back from the midterm evaluation.

Therefore, in this report we will focus on the description of the works carried out in WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP6.

2. Role of the deliverable in the Workpackage and in the project

The INCULTUM project started on 1 May 2021. The first reporting period ran from 1 May 2021 to 30 April 2022. As a summary of the second project year, the D1.3 Progress report was presented. In this Final public report, we therefore present the last year results of INCULTUM.

The interrelation between the different WPs, tasks and partners has been fundamental in the development of the project. This has been a crucial element in the development of the work, enriching the results. On the other hand, this advantage becomes a challenge when it comes to producing a final report of these characteristics, where we present a last year summary, in which we also try not to repeat information. In any case, we show here the final activities of each WP, as the culmination of a project that we consider has had a great impact (and will continue to have it) on the cultural tourism of marginal and peripheral areas.

3. Work development by WP

As this report is a summary of the activities carried out during last year project, we can proudly announce that all the tasks set out in the GA have been successfully completed.

WP 1: Project Management

During the last year of the project last task in this WP have been successfully concluded. We have continued to hold informal meetings between the pilots, putting different pilots in contact with each other in order to foster interrelation and dialogue and, in this way, favour knowledge between the different study areas of the project. We can say that this format of informal meetings has been very fruitful as it has allowed fluid dialogues generating trust between partners to discuss issues and share experiences. We have had the advantage of coordinating the project (WP1-UGR) at the same time as leading WP 5, which has favoured this good harmony with the pilots. Other partners have always been present at the informal meetings, specifically representatives of WP2 (dissemination and communication), as well as the WP 7 (Impact) team, who were also interested in getting first-hand knowledge of the work in the pilots.

The last meeting of the INCULTUM Consortium (**T1.1. Consortium plenary meetings**) has taken place between 11-13 April 2024, in Guadix (Granada. Spain). It has been a very participative meeting in which we have not followed the usual scheme, in which each WP lead partner presented its results, and in which the pilots

made a summary of the work done. In this case, from the organisation of the project, satisfied with the good work done by the partners who have more than fulfilled the expectations, we decided to focus the final meeting of the consortium on the final review of the project. We have focused on aspects of impact achieved, administrative aspects necessary for the closure of the project, and a very interesting and fruitful discussion on one of the deliverables that have been delivered at the end of the project, the D4.5 Policy outputs (which we will see later).

On 12th April we held the International Conference: Visiting the margins: INnovative CULTural ToUrisM in European peripheries, hosted in ENTURNA Escuela Internacional de Turismo Rural y Naturaleza (International School of Rural Tourism. Guadix. Granada. Spain). The programme is available in the project's website (<https://incultum.eu/dissemination/incultum-international-conference/>). Given that the GA envisaged that the event will combine know-how and innovation exchange with business-matching sessions for cultural, creative and tourism entrepreneurs, at the same time we held a poster session¹ where the pilots and the invited projects showed their main features. All the posters are also available in the [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#).

Respecting to the internal management of the project we have to indicate that all the deliverables have been uploaded on time and following the Quality plan (**T1.3 Quality management**), where the reports had to be reviewed by a non-author partner, giving in this way an extra quality point.

The monitoring and support from the INCULTUM (UGR) management team has been useful and fruitful. Throughout the project we have been supporting the partners in the completion of the tasks and keeping an eye on the deadlines so that there were no significant delays (**T1.2. Progress and assessment and periodic reporting**). The daily contact with the partners has favoured the creation of a proactive and generous working group, which we believe can be seen in the results of the project. Also throughout the project, a six-monthly report has been requested from the partners in order to have an update on the activities that were being carried out. In these midterm reports, information was also requested regarding possible problems in terms of financial management or other project related issues. The **communication with European Commission (T1.4)** through our PO has been very fruitful and useful to solve doubts that emerged during the development of the project.

¹ <https://incultum.eu/digital-poster-gallery/>

WP 2: Communication and Dissemination

As the tasks of this WP have lasted for the whole project, we can refer to its last deliverable to obtain the most accurate information on the results obtained. This deliverable is **D2.3. Report on dissemination and communication.**

The task of this deliverable, correctly finished are:

- T1.2 Communication and dissemination strategy (M1-36)
- T2.2 Web presence (M1-36)
- T2.3 Promotional materials and publications (M1-36). One of the tasks included here is **INCULTUM Book (D2.4)**, please see this deliverable for more information about the book.
- T2.4 Events promotion (M1-36)
- T2.5 Local communication (M4-36)

It is important to note that despite the end of the project, both the blog and the website continue to be updated with activities from both the pilots and the project itself, which are being finalised in the last few weeks.

WP 3: Data analysis and statistics

The task of this WP have been:

- **T3.1. Data collection (M1-24)**
- **T3.2. Data analysis (M13-36)**

In WP3, SDU team have been working extensively on the collection of data on tourism from alternative sources to supplement the survey data collected by the Pilots, in order to complete the WP tasks and deliverables. To assist the Pilots in the preparation of the visitor surveys, a template with possible questions to ask were created a , in order to obtain comparable metrics from each Pilot, to be used in the final analysis.

The first part of the data collection consisted in the collection of official statistics to describe urban and regional development in the pilot regions as well as measures of tourism.

The second part of the data collection has concentrated on alternative sources. The result is a large database of reviews and attractions from the platform Tripadvisor which is available open access once INCULTUM is completed and the work carried out in this part covers the milestone MS14 (<https://zenodo.org/records/10934854>). To facilitate the use of the database we have also prepared a comprehensive data manual explaining the data collection process and summarizing the included variables, and a readme file with metadata to explain each component of the

database. The data has been collected for all countries included in the INCULTUM and observations cover the individual attractions. With this data at hand, we have analyzed tourism in the areas where the Pilots are located and identified control regions to be used as a counterfactual in the evaluation of the impact the INCULTUM. As part of the collection of these data, we have validated the data to establish that they are indeed representative of tourism. We have compared the data with official statistics from Eurostat on arrivals in each country and found a strong correlation. This indicates that the Tripadvisor data describes tourism flows well and supports our use of this alternative source. The database has been used in **D3.3 Findings analysis report** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10894343>), to analyze the impact of INCULTUM in the pilot regions.

The main challenge in this regard has been the various difficulties experienced by the pilots, during the process of the survey data collection. During the first round, many of the Pilots experienced various difficulties. To overcome some of these difficulties, we discussed them with the Pilots and the results could be seen during the subsequent rounds of data collection. In the second round, which covered the autumn 2022 and winter 2023, 8 out of 10 Pilots could send us their results, while in the third and final round all but one pilot had some survey results ready.

Another major challenge in the completion of D3.3 and to a lesser extent D3.2, has been the fact that the tourism sector was hit very hard by the Covid-19 pandemic. This has made the identification of a causal effect of the pilot action almost impossible since the general recovery of the tourism sector coincides with the start of the INCULTUM pilot action.

To overcome this second challenge, SDU team have focused on general trends in tourism in the pilot areas, instead of estimating precise effects. The result is a detailed analysis of tourism trends in the pilot areas together with a descriptive comparison with identified control regions. The results show that in general the pilot areas are peripheral and usually below the national and European averages in terms of economic development, as measures by urbanization, unemployment, and regional income. Tourism in the Pilot areas varies across the Pilots, where one distinctive factor is the proximity to the sea. Even though, hard to say with certainty, the results obtained from our analysis in D3.3, indicates that the Pilot action might have helped these areas to regain in tourism after the Covid-19 pandemic.

Included in WP3 are Deliverables 3.1 DMP and D3.4 Data Management Plan-final version (<https://zenodo.org/records/11065188>). For more information on this deliverable we refer to this report.

WP 4: Policies and participatory models

WP4 has successfully addressed the critical role of participatory models in fostering sustainable tourism development. Acknowledging the limitations of traditional top-down decision-making approaches, this WP and its subsequent tasks highlight using of participatory models that aim to distribute power more evenly among all stakeholders involved in tourism development. This shift seeks to ensure that tourism development benefits all parties and aligns with broader goals of sustainability.

The WP4 tasks of the last year of the project have been:

- **Task 4.3 Evaluation framework for the assessment of participatory models' (M13-36)** outcomes that are based on co-creation of innovative tools in relation to the expected benefits for the involved stakeholders. The implementation of this task relates to the remaining four tasks in this WP. The main deliverable of this task is **D4.4 Evaluation framework for participatory models** (<https://zenodo.org/records/11061109>). Recognizing the diversity among stakeholders—government bodies, local communities, academia, tourists, media outlets—and their varying motivations is fundamental. This heterogeneity influences participatory processes and their outcomes, necessitating an evaluation that encompasses these varied expectations and interests. Assessing participatory models in cultural tourism requires a comprehensive strategy, examining innovative tools, outcomes, stakeholder expectations, and collaborative engagement. Both process and outcome evaluations are vital, reflecting their interconnectedness and contribution to sustainable cultural tourism.

The systematic evaluation framework integrates various facets to thoroughly assess participatory models. Beginning with context-specific factors, stakeholders could be engaged through interviews, surveys, and focus groups to collect data on both internal and external contextual influences. Qualitative analysis is then applied to these insights, developing a deeper understanding of how these factors impact the effectiveness of participatory processes.

Stakeholder identification and expectations are crucial, employing stakeholder mapping alongside surveys and interviews to compile expectations and motivations. This data undergoes analysis to highlight common themes and potential conflicts or alignments, leading to the formulation of a comprehensive stakeholder profile that encapsulates their expectations and motivations.

The evaluation extends to both process and outcome, utilizing mixed methods to assess mechanisms, stakeholder engagement, and the qualitative and quantitative impact of outcomes. This dual analysis helps identify the participatory models' strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

The level of participation needs to be measured to understand the degree of stakeholder engagement and contribution, identifying trends and influencing factors to strategize for enhanced participation.

Furthermore, balancing stakeholder interests involves gathering data on their diverse perspectives, goals, and motivations. This information is analysed to discern areas of alignment and divergence, crafting strategies for fostering collaboration among stakeholders and developing recommendations for a collaborative environment conducive to achieving shared objectives.

By embracing this robust and comprehensive method, the task 4.3 seeks to investigate the participatory models' effectiveness, stakeholder engagement, and strategies for balancing diverse interests thoroughly. This approach provides a solid foundation for enhancing the participatory models in cultural tourism, aiming to evaluate and refine these initiatives effectively.

- **Task 4.4 Policy brief, think papers and recommendations regarding instruments for participatory models leading to synergies between participatory models and innovative tools arrangements (M12-36).**

Utilizing the inventory compiled in previous tasks, along with focus group conclusions and findings from WP3/WP5, the team developed policy recommendations, innovative ideas, guidelines, strategies, and tools. These were then discussed and systematized. Key objectives and deliverables included within this task are as follows:

- Policy Toolbox for Participatory Models (<https://incultum.eu/policy-toolbox/>), assembled from various deliverables and outputs of this WP, offers a wide range of tools for policymakers, practitioners, and academics. It features several participatory frameworks tailored to identify drivers and barriers across different models and includes an evaluation framework for their assessment. This comprehensive toolbox helps in understanding and enhancing participatory models effectively. The creation of this toolbox also response to the MS15 and as an achievement of one of the objective of WP4
- Policy recommendations to enhance synergies was organised through the project objective to establish synergies between participatory models and innovative tool arrangements. This effort resulted in Deliverable **D4.5 Policy outputs** (This deliverable is consists of two think papers ([Think paper 1: Cultural and sustainable tourism, a territorial development tool for Europe's rural areas](#), [Think paper 2 Heritage communities at the heart of rural heritage development](#)

[projects](#) and one policy brief ([Policy recommendations for tourism to be a tool for inclusive and sustainable territorial projects in marginal areas](#)) and Milestone 15 (Policy toolbox for participatory models).

A notable innovation introduced by INCULTUM is the "Sustainable Tourism Wheel": <https://zenodo.org/records/10955921>. This model promotes incremental improvements in stakeholder engagement, skills, and contributions through a virtuous cycle with four strategic stages: (1) Revealing and strengthening the community's common ground, (2) Organizing common ground management and community development, (3) Organizing the tourism offer, and (4) Marketing the tourism offer.

These steps ensure that policy recommendations not only address local, regional/national, and European levels but are also pragmatically implementable and aimed at tangible improvements in the field of sustainable tourism and community engagement.

WP 5: Communities of practice, innovative tools and pilot solutions

For the last year tasks performed on the pilots (**T5.3 Fieldwork second stage. M19-36**) we refer the reader to **D5.2 Final pilots report** (<https://zenodo.org/records/11071058>).

WP 6: Training and networking

WP6 tasks carried out in the last year of the project have been:

- **T6.1 Local training (M13-33):** The University of Pisa, in collaboration with Promoter, has developed the [INCULTUM Training Portal](#), an online platform dedicated to providing diverse training resources to a broad audience, including local stakeholders, university students, researchers, public administrators, business development professionals, tourism experts, and cultural heritage managers. The portal offers a wide array of training materials aimed at enhancing the skills and knowledge of its users in sustainable tourism, cultural heritage preservation, innovative participatory methods and community engagement. Within the portal there is an interesting section dedicated to [local training](#) with resources provided by the pilots themselves. Among the primary objectives of the INCULTUM project, as well as a key element for the sustainable development of tourist destinations, is the involvement of the local community in the planning and development actions of the tourist destination: objectives that have led to the development and organisation of training activities with the operators. Starting in May 2023, two meetings were organised (<https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/>

[first-training-session-of-incultums-san-pellegrino-in-alpe/](#)), designed as training events for the operators, but above all an opportunity to share ideas, opinions and suggestions. This created a relationship of trust between the research team and the local operators, so much so that positive ideas were also developed for the village, such as the creation of tourist information brochures and their printing, financed by the operators themselves.

- **T6.2 Guidelines on the use of European Structural and Investment Funds (M19-33).** The results of this task addressed to complete deliverable **D6.2. Guidelines on the use of European Structural and Investment Funds** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10843175>). SDU team also surveyed the Pilots about their experience with European Structural Funds, to create indications of best practice and common pitfalls during the application for these funds. This report were disseminated in form of poster (<https://zenodo.org/records/10843423>) which highlights the main findings and recommendations of the deliverable. This poster was included in the poster session of the INCULTUM International Conference (<https://incultum.eu/dissemination/incultum-international-conference/>).
- **T6.3. Community building and networking (M3-36).** This task has been carried out during all the project extension. And to avoid repetition we address the reader to the D.6.3 INCULTUM Network.
- **T6.4 Training methodology and coordination (M3-33).** The University of Pisa is leading this WP, and had the task of creating training opportunities at an international level, in the form of video-courses focusing on cultural heritage and the active participation of the local community in tourism planning. The target audience will be university students and researchers who are in various capacities part of the consortium. Right from the early stages of development of the course, developed by Prof. Gavinelli at the request of the University of Pisa, the research team got in touch with possible professionals in the sector to be interviewed, researched additional information materials (FIMs), and provided support in drafting part of the course content. The modules into which the course was developed are:
 - INTRODUCTION TO THE COURSE
 - SECTION 1: Marketing and branding principles
 - SECTION 2: Promotion and storytelling
 - SECTION 3: Local involvement and place representation

As anticipated, in addition to the video lecture sessions and interviews with experts in the field, there are also quizzes that allow the student's self-assessment, as well as additional information materials (FIMs), for those who wish to delve more deeply into the proposed topics.

Initially, it was difficult to find an online platform that would allow the team to create the digital content for the course and then make it available to those

who would use it, nevertheless a solution was found thanks to a technological tool provided by Pisa University. The results, however, have been satisfactory, with a course that can be used by all and divided in a way that suits academics and non-academics alike, a comprehensive portal on the subject with various resources.

The course "[The importance of marketing and social branding in tourism destination](#)" is completely available in Zenodo INCULTUM Community.

WP 7: Impact, evaluation and exploitation plan

For the latest tasks carried out in this WP (**T7.2 Impact, evaluation and result exploitation plan** - M7-35 - and **T7.3 Exploitation activities evaluation** - M13-36-), as well as their final conclusions, we refer the reader to **D7.3 Updated plan for the impact evaluation and exploitation of results** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10980453>).

4. Additional outputs in INCULTUM project

As stated in the GA "INCULTUM will use Open-AIRE, the repository for scientific publications, an online archive and Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe". Accordingly with what exposed on the GA, in relation with Open Access to scientific publications is said "Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results". In particular, it must:

- deposit a machine readable electronic copy of the manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;
- ensure open access to the deposited publication:
 - o on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher
 - o within twelve months for publications in any other case.
- ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata ("European Union (EU)" and "Horizon 2020"; name of the action, acronym and grant number; publication date; persistent identifier).

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the beneficiaries must: (I) deposit in a research data repository and make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate— free of charge for any user — the following: the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications; other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the DMP. (II) Also they

have to provide information — via the repository — about tools necessary for validating the results.

With all these obligations set out in the AG, we consider it necessary to hold a workshop on Open Access/data to have a collective discussion about how to proceed with this requests. The attendance different teams' members was very important. The workshop (21st March 2024) was carried out by the Eachtra Archaeological projects team, which was also in charge of the pilot #9 and the drafting of the DMP. The proposal to the partners was clear: to create a Community in Zenodo platform. With this decision we were also responding to the request of our Innovation manager about the way we publish the grey literature produced by the project, and the current lack of tools needed to produce bibliographic reference. All partners agreed to take this step.

WHY DO WE USE ZENODO?

ZENODO is the repository of the Open-AIRE ecosystem, which allows researchers to archive and share their research objects (data, software, publications, and other research outputs). The characteristics of this platform are appropriate to comply with the provisions of the AG:

- Used to ensure long-term storage, metadata consistency and easy sharing (DOI, metrics, statistics)
- For storage, not for data consultation, like Tableau or Carto
- Formats accepted: publications (book, book section, conference paper, journal article, patent, preprint, report, thesis, technical note, working paper, etc.), posters, presentations, datasets, images (figures, plots, drawings, diagrams, photos), software, videos/audio and interactive materials such as lessons
- Up to 50GB per dataset
- Uploaded content cannot be changed, just versioned; metadata can be edited.

The collaboration of all partners has been invaluable in order to have most of the outputs, datasets and publications uploaded to Zenodo for the conclusion of the project. In this way, the results generated by all the partners and which are currently open in the Zenodo INCULTUM Community, are 100% accessible to anyone who wants to consult them.

At the end of the project these are more than 130 items uploaded in the [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#):

- Deliverables. We upload those deliverables which consider as part of final results of the project, no those one which had an intermediate phase during the development of the project.
- Presentations: relevant presentations of project partners in congress or conferences. We include also the presentations of INCULTUM Final Conference (held in Guadix on 12 April 2024)
- Leaflets, maps, or brochure from INCULTUM Pilots dissemination of results (cultural routes, etc).
- Innovation factsheets of each pilot.
- Datasets: questionnaires, surveys, gps tracks, cultural routes, etc.

As also mentioned in the AG there are some exceptions that allow for various reasons not to publish in Open Access. Some partners have invoked these articles in order not to publish some of their data. For more details see page 18 of the DMP (<https://zenodo.org/records/11065188>).

5. Conclusion

We consider that the completion of the INCULTUM project has been a very successful culmination of 3 years of work. We have had the opportunity to establish relationships with partners from all over Europe and to work in peripheral areas that hide a great tourism potential that still needs to be discovered. Partners shared their experiences during the last face-to-face meeting in Guadix on the 11th of April. Many agreed that now that the pilots are starting to work and local stakeholders have gained confidence in the project, the project is coming to an end. But it is also an incentive to continue working and that what has been sown in the territories will bear fruit in the medium and long term. The impacts that the project has had on the pilot territories will be seen in the coming months and years. In many cases, the work will serve to promote sustainable tourism and support local communities in revaluing their historical and cultural heritage, empowering them.

Regarding the management of the project, we can point out that the working group of INCULTUM partners has been growing in involvement and generosity. The good results are clear examples of the good relationship and harmony with which we have worked.